

Mono- and Binuclear Dioxomolybdenum(VI) Complexes with Polydentate Schiff Base Ligands

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Molybdenum, the only metal among the heavier transition elements which has a major role as a trace element in enzymes, forms several mono- and binuclear complexes, which may be termed as classical or Wernerian and also has a rich chemistry of metal-metal bonded compounds, called non-classical or non-Wernerian complexes. In this paper several mono-nuclear complexes of MoO_3^{2+} are reported to be formed with the tridentate ligands, H_3L ($\text{H}_3\text{L} = \text{H}_3\text{SAE}, \text{H}_3\text{SAP}, \text{H}_3\text{SAPT}$). In presence of imidazole ligands, the interaction of $\text{MoO}_3(\text{acac})$, and the tridentate ligands form *cis*-octahedral complexes of the type $[\text{MoO}_3(\text{L})(\text{Im})]$. The tetra-, penta and hexadentate ligands, $\text{H}_2\text{L}-\text{L}$ ($\text{H}_2\text{LL} = \text{H}_2\text{DMED}, \text{H}_2\text{DMPD}$ and H_2DMDT) react with $\text{MoO}_3(\text{acac})$, to form binuclear and octahedral *cis*-dioxomolybdenum complexes $[(\text{acac})\text{MoO}_3(\text{L}-\text{L})\text{O}(\text{acac})]$, by the partial replacement of the acac groups from the starting $\text{MoO}_3(\text{acac})_3$. These complexes have been adequately characterised by ir, nmr (^1H and ^{13}C), cyclic voltammetric and thermogravimetric measurements.

Molybdenum is one of the most unique elements among the transition elements of the second and third transition series¹. It exhibits a variety of oxidation states ranging from -1 to +6 and consequently, has a wide range of stereochemistries² rendering its chemistry to be the most complex among the transition elements. It is the only element among the heavier transition elements which appears to have a major role as a trace element in enzymes. Several aspects of molybdenum chemistry have been widely studied to gain a better understanding of its biological relevance. Indeed, the importance and topical relevance of molybdenum can be better appreciated by realising that it is one of the few elements which currently has its own series of international conferences³. Both molybdenum and tungsten are chemically similar, although there are some differences, and there is much less similarity in comparison with chromium. Although molybdenum exhibits a variety of oxidation states, the +6 state is the most stable and forms a large number of coordination complexes. The chemistry of hexavalent molybdenum is dominated by the oxo ligand and its analogues. This highest oxidation state of molybdenum requires for its stabilisation the presence of ligands that are not only good *sigma*-donors but also good *pi*-donors, such that sufficient charge density can be placed on the molybdenum to avoid violating the Pauling electroneutrality principle⁴. This necessitates the utilisation of ligands with filled *p*-orbitals that are not otherwise engaged in bonding with other atoms, giving a situation in which a multiple bond is formed between the molybdenum and its donor ligand. The oxo ligand, O^{2-} , stabilises a large number of formally molybdenum(VI) complexes, although it has been realised now that the sulphido, S^{2-} , selenido, Se^{2-} , peroxido, O_2^{2-} , persulphido, S_2^{2-} , imido, NR^{2-} and the nitrido, N^{3-} as well as

the hydrazido, R_2NN^{2-} and hydroxylamido, R_2NO^- , etc. ions can form complexes that may be regarded as analogues in oxo chemistry. The structural chemistry of molybdenum(VI) complexes with these analogous ligands can be extrapolated from the oxo chemistry.

Some classical non-Wernerian complexes of molybdenum(VI)

Mononuclear complexes dominate the simple coordination chemistry of molybdenum(VI), precisely due to the absence of *d*-electrons in molybdenum(VI) that precludes the formation of metal-metal bonds between the two molybdenum(VI) centres. In oxo complexes of hexavalent molybdenum, MoO_4^{4+} , MoO_3^{3+} and MoO_3 structural units are usually encountered. Although, MoO_4^{4+} ^{5,6} and MoO_3 ^{7,8} are known only in a relatively small number of molybdenum(VI) complexes, complexes containing the MoO_3^{3+} core are by far the most common in molybdenum(VI) chemistry⁹⁻¹¹. The vast majority of such complexes are six-coordinate and mostly of distorted octahedral structure with the oxygens mutually *cis*, thereby maximising the $\text{O}(p\pi) \rightarrow \text{Mo}(d\pi)$ bonding where the MoO_3^{3+} group is reminiscent of the uranyl ion, UO_2^{2+} , though its chemistry is by no means as extensive and the latter is a linear ion. The $\text{Mo}-\text{O}_i$ distances generally lie at $1.70 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}$ and $\text{O}_i-\text{Mo}-\text{O}_j$ angles lie at $106 \pm 3^\circ$. Complexes containing MoO_3^{3+} unit are characterised by two infrared stretching frequencies in the $880-950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region corresponding to symmetric and anti-symmetric $\text{Mo}-\text{O}_i$ stretching vibrations. Interestingly, the EXAFS studies are consistent with the presence of this group in certain enzymes^{12,13}.

Although numerous examples of Schiff base complexes of lighter transition elements are well known¹⁴, relatively less were reported on the cor-

responding molybdenum complexes. However, in recent years several *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes of several bi-, tri- and tetradentate Schiff base ligands are reported to simulate many characteristic properties of the active sites of molybdo-enzymes. Thus, the bidentate ligands (H_2L) form MoO_2L_2 complexes^{15,16} while the tetradentate ligands (H_2L'')^{17,18} form complexes of the type MoO_2L'' . Several tridentate Schiff base ligands (H_3L') form complexes¹⁹⁻²² which are coordinatively unsaturated and accept a monodentate donor ligand (D) forming complexes of the type $[MoO_2(L')(D)]$.

For past several years, the work in this laboratory has been concentrated on dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes with Schiff base ligands possessing multidentate donor sites. $MoO_2(acac)_2$ was employed as a very convenient source of the MoO_2^{2+} ion and could be prepared easily either from Na_2MoO_4 ²³ or from $(NH_4)_6Mo_7O_{24} \cdot 4H_2O$ ^{19,24} and acetylacetonate by adjusting the pH. In all cases, 'acac' in $MoO_2(acac)_2$ behaved as an innocent ligand and could be either partly or totally replaced by other ligands. Tri-, tetra-, penta- and hexadentate Schiff base ligands were used for complex formation with the MoO_2^{2+} core. Although possibilities existed for the formation of mono- or binuclear complexes containing the MoO_2^{2+} core or binuclear complexes containing the Mo_2O_5 and Mo_3O_8 core structures^{25,26}, in all cases we obtained either mononuclear complexes or binuclear complexes that contained the MoO_2^{2+} core. Indeed, with the tridentate Schiff base ligands only mononuclear complexes were formed, whereas with the tetra-, penta- and hexadentate ligands it was seen that these ligands bridge the two MoO_2^{2+} core units, forming binuclear complexes.

Mononuclear mixed ligand complexes with tridentate Schiff bases and imidazole

Since the discovery of a group of ligands by Schiff²⁷, a wide range of Schiff base ligands have been synthesised and their complexation behaviour studied keeping in view their great synthetic flexibility and diverse structural aspects¹⁴. The multidentate Schiff bases are of importance as it has been recognised that in many of the natural processes, multidentate ligands are mostly used for important enzymatic and biological reactions, and also are used to form extractable or volatile complexes. The biologically important ligand, imidazole, is both a good σ -donor and a π -acceptor and is known to play a vital role in many biological systems where it is found in the amino acid histidine, which has been implicated in the active sites of enzymes^{28,29}. With this in the background and in view of the fact that mixed ligand complexes play an important role in many naturally occurring biological processes³⁰, work in this laboratory has been directed at the synthesis and characterisation of mixed-ligand complex formation of MoO_2^{2+} with several dibasic, tridentate Schiff bases and imidazole or its derivatives. The reaction of a dibasic, triden-

tate ligand with MoO_2^{2+} renders the sixth coordination site vacant in the electrically neutral molybdenum(vi) complex and this vacant site may be envisaged as providing a suitable bonding site for the substrates during a catalytic cycle. The tridentate ligands employed were obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with 2-amino-1-ethanol (H_2SAE)³¹, 2-aminophenol (H_2SAP)¹⁹ and 2-aminothiophenol (H_2SAPT)^{32,33}.

An ethanolic solution of the dibasic, tridentate ligand (H_2SAE , H_2SAP or H_2SAPT) reacts with calculated molar proportions of $MoO_2(acac)_2$ in presence of imidazole base leading to the removal of both the acetylacetonate groups forming the complex $[MoO_2(H_2SB)(L)]$, ($H_2SB=SAE, SAP, SAPT$; $L=Im$). The release of the acetylacetonate groups during the course of synthesis has been confirmed by the isolation of $Cu(acac)_2$ quantitatively from the filtrate after the reaction of $MoO_2(acac)_2$ with H_2SAE , H_2SAP or H_2SAPT and imidazole ligands. Further confirmation for the formation of these compounds has been obtained from ir and nmr (¹H and ¹³C) data.

The $[MoO_2(SAE)L]$ complexes: All these compounds³⁴ are yellow diamagnetic and non-electrolytic. The ligand H_2SAE has an intense band at 1638 cm^{-1} assigned to coupled ν_{C-N} vibrations³¹ which is shifted to lower frequencies and appears as a split band in the region close to 1600 cm^{-1} , suggesting coordination as an anionic ligand through the O and N atoms^{35,36}. The aromatic ν_{C-O} and the aliphatic ν_{C-O} vibrations occur at 1550 and 1040 cm^{-1} , respectively. The broad hydrogen bonded OH stretch near 2700 cm^{-1} of the free ligand is absent in the complexes, suggesting coordination of the ligand as a deprotonated, dianionic ligand. The formation of Mo-O bonds with the Schiff base results in the appearance of a few medium to strong bonds in $550-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region³⁷, and formation of Mo-N bonds with the Schiff base and imidazole results in the appearance of additional bands in $520-600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region¹⁹. The *trans*- MoO_2^{2+} configuration would have resulted in a single $\nu_{Mo=O}$ band.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the ligand and the complexes show that aldiminic proton ($-N=CH-$) appears as one proton singlet at 8.19 ppm in the ligand^{31,38}, shifting somewhat downfield to 8.67 ppm for the complexes. The aromatic protons are observed as a multiplet central around 7.5 ppm. The methylene signals of the ligand backbone are seen as two sets of triplets at ca. 3.89 and 4.51 ppm in the complexes. The imidazole protons in the complexes appear³⁹ at 7.84, 7.08 and 7.07 ppm for H-2, H-4 and H-5 respectively, and the signals for the substituents in the imidazole ring are appropriately assigned (Table 1).

The ¹³C nmr spectra of the complexes very clearly reveal the coordination of the ligand to the MoO_2^{2+} core. The signal at ca. 209.9 ppm is due to the aldiminic carbon and the signals at 164.9, 163.6, 135.3, 134.7, 122.1, and 119.8 correspond

TABLE 1—¹H NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF [MoO₂(SAE)(L)] COMPLEXES*

Compd.	SAE protons				Imidazole protons			R
	-N=CH	-C ₂ H ₅	-N-CH ₂	-N-CH ₂ -CH ₂	H-2	H-4	H-5	
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(Im)]	8.67	7.5	3.89	4.51	7.84	7.08	7.07	
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-MeIm)]	8.64	7.4	3.81	4.47	7.83	7.08	7.07	2.4
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-EtIm)]	8.65	7.3	3.86	4.49	7.83	7.08	7.06	1.3, 4.0
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-ViIm)]	8.62	7.5	3.88	4.45	7.84	7.07	7.06	5.14, 5.46, 6.95
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-AlIm)]	8.66	7.4	3.87	4.48	7.82	7.08	7.07	4.05, 5.46, 5.80

Measurements in (OD₂)₂CO at ambient temperature. All values in ppm downfield to TMS.TABLE 2—¹³C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF [MoO₂(SAE)(L)] COMPLEXES

Compd.	SAE carbons				Imidazole carbons			R
	-N=CH	-C ₂ H ₅	-N-CH ₂	-N-CH ₂ -CH ₂	C-2	C-4	C-5	
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(Im)]	209.9	164.9- 119.8	72.66	61.66	135.7	120.7	119.8	
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-EtIm)]	209.5	164.5- 119.6	72.59	61.58	135.5	119.9	119.8	15.82, 44.62
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-ViIm)]	209.7	164.6- 119.4	72.61	61.60	135.3	120.1	119.9	105.42, 130.84
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-AlIm)]	209.3	164.1- 119.2	72.58	61.59	135.6	120.6	119.7	49.98, 118.21, 133.51

*All measurements in (CD₃)₂CO; all in ppm relative to internal (CD₃)₂CO resonating at 29.2 ppm downfield to TMS.

to the carbons of the aromatic ring. The methylene carbons of the ligand backbone appear at 61.6 and 72.6 ppm. The ¹³C signals in the complexes at 135.7, 120.7 and 119.8 ppm are assigned to the C-2, C-4 and C-5 respectively, of the heterocyclic imidazole ring³⁹. The signals for the substituents in the imidazole ring are also appropriately assigned (Table 2). The ¹³C nmr spectra of [MoO₂(SAE)(Im)] complex in (CD₃)₂CO is shown in Fig. 1.

(I)

(II)

Fig. 1. The ligand H₂SAE (I) and its complex with MoO₂²⁺ (II).

Mass spectral investigations do not reveal any information as the complexes do not ionise under

the conditions in the mass spectrometer and no molecular ion peak of the complexes is obtained. The cyclic voltammetric measurements provide the values for cathodic reduction potentials. The complexes do not show any observable oxidation wave upon the reverse anodic scan in the cyclic voltammogram showing irreversible redox behaviour. This is not very unusual as many *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes^{40,41} have generally shown irreversible or quasi-reversible behaviour. The cathodic reduction potentials in CH₃CN medium are all obtained in the narrow range of -1.1 to -1.2 V vs Ag/AgCl (Table 3). The cyclic voltammogram for a typical complex [MoO₂(SAE)(1-EtIm)] is shown in Fig. 2 as an example of what is observed for these complexes. The thermogravimetric analysis of the complexes reveals their stability at room temperature and also shows the absence of lattice water. All of them are stable upto 150-190° and show no signs of decomposition. With increase in temperature,

TABLE 3—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRY DATA FOR [MoO₂(SAE)(L)] COMPLEXES IN CH₃CN

Compd.	E _{pc} V*
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(Im)]	-1.10
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-EtIm)]	-1.16
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-ViIm)]	-1.20
[MoO ₂ (SAE)(1-AlIm)]	-1.18

*V vs Ag/AgCl

Fig. 2 ^{13}C nmr spectrum of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAE})(\text{Im})]$ complex in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$.

the imidazole ligands are lost in a stepwise manner, finally forming MoO_3 as the stable end product at 550° .

TABLE 4—PROMINENT IR BANDS (cm^{-1}) FOR THE $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(\text{L})]$ COMPLEXES*

Compd.	(SAP) vibration		MoO_2^{2+} vibration
	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	
H_2SAP	1 632	1 532	—
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(\text{EtOH})]$	1 608	1 560	928, 910
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(\text{Im})]$	1 612, 1 605	1 555	560 920, 905
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(1\text{-MeIm})]$	1 610, 1 605	1 555	560 920, 900
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(1\text{-EtIm})]$	1 616, 1 605	1 550	562 928, 900
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(1\text{-ViIm})]$	1 612, 1 600	1 550	560 922, 900
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(1\text{-AlIm})]$	1 615, 1 605	1 555	560 928, 905
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(2\text{-MeIm})]$	1 612, 1 602	1 550	558 920, 888
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(2\text{-EtIm})]$	1 612, 1 602	1 552	558 916, 895
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(2\text{-PrIm})]$	1 612, 1 605	1 555	558 918, 895
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(1,2\text{-DiMeIm})]$	1 615, 1 605	1 550	560 920, 910
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(1\text{-Vi}, 2\text{-MeIm})]$	1 612	1 548	558 928, 905
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(4\text{-MeIm})]$	1 615, 1 605	1 550	560 930, 880

*In KBr.

The $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})\text{L}]$ complexes: An ethanolic solution of H_2SAP reacts with the calculated molar proportions of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2]$ leading to the removal of both 'acac' groups forming the complex $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(\text{EtOH})]$ which retains the *cis*-dioxo bonds. This compound, on reaction with imidazole ligands in EtOH, undergoes ligand exchange (equation 1) to form yellow, red or brown crystalline solids $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{SAP})(\text{L})]^{42}$, where L = imidazole or its derivatives. Steric constraints would favour the tridentate ligand spanning only the three meridional positions and not the isomeric facial positions. The imidazole ligand is *trans* to one of the oxo groups.

These are non-electrolytic and diamagnetic compounds and the electronic spectra in MeOH gave bands with molar extinction coefficients of 16 090 ($\lambda=300$) and 9 000 ($\lambda=450$ nm). Beyond 500 nm, the optical density values were extensively low and there was no evidence of any *d-d* transition over the visible range. The ir spectra reveal that the bands due to imidazole derivatives occur in almost identical positions and can be easily assigned⁴³. For the Schiff bases, the broad hydrogen-bonded OH stretch near $2\,500\text{--}2\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the free ligand, is absent in the complexes, suggesting its coordination as a deprotonated, dianionic ligand. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of the free Schiff base is split in the complexes giving two bands at $1\,612\text{--}1\,616$ and $1\,600\text{--}1\,605\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a fairly strong band at $1\,550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complex is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of the Schiff base ligand. The

TABLE 5—¹H NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF [MoO₂(SAPT)(L)] COMPLEXES*

Compd.	H ₂ SAPT protons		Imidazole protons			R
	N=CH	C ₂ H ₅	H-2	H-4	H-5	
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(Im)]	8.21	6.8–7.0	7.40	7.21	7.08	1.87,
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-EtIm)]	8.28	6.5–7.1	7.92	7.18	7.20	4.08
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-ViIm)]	8.36	6.7–6.9	7.88	7.24	7.16	5.14,
						5.46,
						6.95
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-AlIm)]	8.24	6.8–7.1	7.96	7.26	7.18	5.07,
						5.09,
						5.63
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(2-MeIm)]	8.40	6.4–6.9		7.16	7.12	2.42

*All measurements in DMSO-d₆ at ambient temperature; all values in ppm downfield to TMS as internal standard.

formation of Mo–O bonds with the Schiff base results in the appearance of a few medium to strong stretching frequencies in the 550–650 cm⁻¹ region³⁵. These complexes show two ir absorption bands due to the *cis*-MoO₂²⁺ group in the 880–920 cm⁻¹ region⁴⁴.

The thermal analysis clearly reveals an endothermic peak for [MoO₂(SAPT)(Im)] complexes, the mass loss of which corresponds to the mass of imidazole ligand. Subsequently, the dianionic Schiff base is lost in stages and ultimately MoO₂ is formed as the stable end-product at ca. 500°. Electrochemical measurements in acetonitrile show very weak responses indicating that the metal centre is not easily reducible.

The [MoO₂(SAPT)L] complexes: The MoO₂(SAPT)L complexes⁴⁵ are light pink or lavender coloured solids, non-electrolytes in DMSO and diamagnetic as expected. The ir spectra do not show any band at 2730 cm⁻¹ due to phenolic OH, suggesting its coordination as a dianionic ligand. Although ir, nmr and mass spectral studies of the ligand show that the ligand exists in the benzothiazoline form^{32,46}, in the present series of complexes the ligand is converted to the Schiff base form on coordination. Prominent bands observed near 1580 cm⁻¹ assigned to the coupled ν_{C=N} and ν_{C=C}¹⁹ and at 1540 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{C=O} (phenolic)²² confirm the coordination through the azomethine nitrogen and the phenolic O⁻ of the deprotonated Schiff base ligand, SAPT. The formation of Mo–O (of the ligand) bond is shown by the appearance of new frequencies in the 550–650 cm⁻¹ region³⁵. A prominent two-band pattern ir spectrum in 900–950 cm⁻¹ region confirms the presence of *cis*-MoO₂²⁺ core structure. The ¹H nmr spectra of the complexes also prove the coordination of the ligands in the Schiff base form (Table 5). The alternating current polarograms of these complexes in DMF medium exhibit two reductive responses. The first reduction occurs at -0.78 to -0.92 V and the second at -1.11 to -1.18 V vs Ag/AgCl (Table 6). The parent MoO₂(SAPT) complex in DMF also undergoes reduction in this potential range. The similarity in the polarograms of the parent MoO₂(SAPT) complex and the imidazole

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of [MoO₂(SAE)(1-EtIm)].

derivatives suggests that the monodentate imidazole ligands are rather easily replaced by the strongly coordinating solvent molecules (DMF)⁴⁷. The ligands do not exhibit any redox activity in the potential range where the molybdenum reductions are observed.

TABLE 6—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA FOR [MoO₂(SAPT)(L)] COMPLEXES

Compd	E _{1/2} V
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(Im)]	-0.78, -1.14
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-EtIm)]	-0.84, -1.18
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-ViIm)]	-0.75, -1.12
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(1-AlIm)]	-0.92, -1.16
[MoO ₂ (SAPT)(2-MeIm)]	-0.89, -1.11

The thermogravimetric analysis clearly shows that the [MoO₂(SAPT)(L)] complexes decompose in a clearly well-defined endothermic step in the temperature range 150–180°, where the mass loss corresponds to the loss of the imidazole ligands. This is also an additional evidence in favour of the relative labile binding of the imidazole ligands in the solid state giving [MoO₂(SAPT)]. On continued heating beyond this stage, total loss of

organic matter occurs in stages ultimately giving MoO_3 as the final product at 500–550°.

Binuclear [(acac)MoO₂(L-L)O₂Mo(acac)] complexes:

The reaction of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$, in suitable solvents, with the multidentate Schiff bases ($\text{H}_2\text{L-L}$) obtained by the condensation of biacetylmonoxime with ethylenediamine (H_2DMED), propylenediamine (H_2DMPD), diethylenetriamine (H_2DMDT) and triethylenetetramine (H_2DMTT) results in the formation of binuclear, mixed-ligand, six-coordinated, *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes [(acac)MoO₂(L-L)O₂Mo(acac)]⁴⁸, by the partial displacement of the acetylacetonate group from the starting $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Structure of the ligands $\text{H}_2\text{L-L}$ (I). Structure of the complexes [(acac)MoO₂(L-L)O₂Mo(acac)] (II).

That only one 'acac' group is displaced from each $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ is confirmed by the isolation of $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ quantitatively from the filtrate after the reaction of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ with the ligands $\text{H}_2\text{L-L}$ ($\text{H}_2\text{L-L} = \text{H}_2\text{DMED}$, H_2DMPD , H_2DMDT , H_2DMTT). Further confirmation of this is also obtained from ir and nmr (¹H and ¹³C) spectra as discussed below. The ligands, $\text{H}_2\text{L-L}$ behave as doubly-deprotonated tetradentate ligands bridging two $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})^+$ centres. A similar partial displacement of 'acac' groups from $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ has also been observed in several complexes containing the MoO_2^{3+} core^{20,49,50}, the VO^{2+} core⁵¹, in complexes of the type $\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{Salen})^{52}$, and also in complexes derived from $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4$ ⁵³. All the complexes synthesised are diamagnetic and non-electrolytic. The

ir bands are characteristic of the *cis*- MoO_2^{3+} core, the Schiff base ligands and the 'acac' groups. In the complexes, a fairly sharp band at 1580–1620 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of the Schiff base ligands⁵⁴. The $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ in the complexes at 1140–1150 cm^{-1} suggests the oximes to be N-coordinated⁵⁵. The $\nu(\text{NO})$ and $\delta_{\text{N-O}}$ bands appear at 1080 and 820 cm^{-1} respectively. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ for the coordinated 'acac' group appears⁵⁶ at 1580 cm^{-1} and the methine C-H bending vibration is seen as a weak band at 1190 cm^{-1} . The formation of Mo-O bonds with 'acac' groups and Mo-N bonds of the Schiff bases results in the appearance of a few medium to strong stretching frequencies in the 550–650 cm^{-1} region, which are absent in the free ligands. As for the *cis*- MoO_2^{3+} groups, the ir spectrum manifests itself in the form of an intense two-band pattern corresponding to the symmetric and antisymmetric Mo=O stretching vibrations^{57,58} in the 880–920 cm^{-1} region. That one or two secondary amine (NH) function remain uncoordinated in the complexes with the pentadentate H_2DMDT and the hexadentate H_2DMTT ligands is seen from the appearance of ν_{NH} at ca. 3150 cm^{-1} . This is further substantiated on the basis of the ¹H nmr spectra discussed below.

The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra establish in a complementary way the disposition of the non-oxo ligands in the complexes. The ¹H nmr spectra of the Schiff base ligands and the complexes show two sharp signals due to the two non-equivalent CH_3 groups in the 1.7–2.0 ppm region and the $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2$ signals at 3.3–3.9 ppm⁵⁹ (Table 7). The ¹³C nmr spectrum of the ligands have two ¹³C signals due to the non-equivalent CH_3 groups at 8.6 and 12.9–13.4 ppm which shift downfield in the complexes to ca. 10.4 and 18.4 ppm respectively. The $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2$ carbons resonate in the 48.9–52.32 ppm region in the free ligands and shift to 42.5–48.9 ppm in the complexes. The carbons (C^c and C^d) in the diacetylmonoxime skeleton resonate at 156.48 and 164.1–165.1 ppm for the free ligands respectively, and shift only slightly downfield in the complexes (Table 8). Additional signals at ca. 2.0 and 5.4 ppm in the ¹H nmr spectrum and at 30.6, 98.7 and 196.7 ppm in the ¹³C nmr spectrum unequivocally demonstrate the presence of coordinated acetylacetonate groups³⁹ in all the complexes. The NH-proton signals in pentadentate H_2DMDT and the hexadentate H_2DMTT ligands appear at 8.3 ppm and in the complexes they shift to 10.5 ppm, providing proof for the presence of free NH groups. Fig. 5 depicts the ¹³C nmr of a typical complex.

The thermal analysis measurements clearly reveals the decomposition patterns of the complexes with increasing temperature, and ultimately in the 650° region MoO_3 is formed as the stable end-product⁴². The analytical data, ir, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral measurements establish the formation of binuclear, ligand-bridged, mixed-ligand, six-coordinated dioxomolybdenum complexes where

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TABLE 7—¹H NMR CHEMICAL SHIFT OF [(acac)MoO₂(L-L)O₂Mo(acac)] COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Schiff base protons				acac protons	
	CH ₃ ^a	CH ₃ ^b	CH ₂ -CH ₂	NH	CH ₃	CH
H ₂ DMED [Mo ₂ O ₄ (acac) ₂ (DMED)]	1.88	2.04	3.75			
	1.78	1.91	3.49		2.1	5.4
H ₂ DMDT [Mo ₂ O ₄ (acac) ₂ (DMDT)]	1.72	1.92	3.43,	8.38		
			3.53,		2.08	5.2
H ₂ DMTT [Mo ₂ O ₄ (acac) ₂ (DMTT)]	1.86	1.93	3.58,	10.55		
			3.80,			
	1.90	1.98	3.27,	8.31		
			3.36,			
			3.42,			
	1.86	1.93	3.49,	10.52	2.14	5.0
			3.64,			
			3.93			

*All measurements in DMSO-d₆; all values in ppm downfield from TMS as internal standard.

TABLE 8—¹³C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFT OF [(acac)MoO₂(L-L)O₂Mo(acac)] COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Schiff base carbons					acac carbons		
	CH ₃ ^a	CH ₃ ^b	CH ₂ -CH ₂	C ^c	C ^d	CH ₃	CH	CO
H ₂ DMED [Mo ₂ O ₄ (acac) ₂ (DMED)]	8.64	12.96	52.32	156.48	165.12			
	10.4	18.22	48.51	164.30	168.54	30.6	98.7	196.7
H ₂ DMDT [Mo ₂ O ₄ (acac) ₂ (DMDT)]	8.64	12.96	49.92,	156.48	164.64			
			51.36					
H ₂ DMTT [Mo ₂ O ₄ (acac) ₂ (DMTT)]	10.07	18.41	46.52,	162.70	166.46	28.9	95.9	194.1
			47.65					
	8.64	13.44	48.96,	156.48	164.16			
			49.92,					
	10.25	18.42	51.84	162.81	167.27	28.6	95.5	193.7
			42.59,					
			45.81,					
			48.92					

*All measurements in DMSO-d₆; all values in ppm relative to internal DMSO-d₆ exhibiting a heptet centred at 39.8 ppm downfield from TMS.

Fig. 5. ¹³C nmr spectrum of [(acac)MoO₂(DMTT)O₂Mo(acac)] complex in DMSO-d₆.

each molybdenum(vi) is surrounded by two oxo-ligands, one bidentate 'acac' group and two N-donor atoms (oxime N and imine N) of the Schiff bases. The potential pentadentate H₂DMDT and the hexadentate H₂DMTT ligands essentially function as bridging tetradentate ligands (like the tetradentate H₂DMED or H₂DMPD) with one or two secondary amine groups (NH) remaining uncoordinated in the complexes. Similar observations have been previously made from this laboratory for thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes.

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